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Alice Growing Up in ‘Temporary Protection’ Land: Immigrant Students’ Identity Development as a Reflection Toward Inclusion Practices

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Abstract

Our aim was to understand the adaptation process, belonging to Turkish culture, ethnic identity development among Syrian students arriving in Turkey and how they develop a sense of belonging and adapt their identities to become integrated into Turkish life and education. In this study, qualitative method and phenomenological research design were preferred. The process of adaptation of immigrant students to a new culture, school and ethnic identity was investigated. Convenience sampling method was preferred, and semi-structured interview form was used as data collection tool. As a result of the content analysis, three categories and 12 concepts related to the adaptation process were revealed. Three concepts were frequently emphasized about the actions of the family in the adaptation process. Six concepts were frequently emphasized about events that led to significant experiences in the school in adaptation process. Three concepts were frequently emphasized about environments’ contributions to adaptation process. Three categories and 16 concepts related to belonging to new culture, school, and class were revealed. Six concepts were frequently emphasized whether they feel part of the new culture. Four concepts were frequently emphasized if they feel belonging to the new school. Six concepts were frequently emphasized whether they feel belonging to the new class. Three categories and 11 concepts related to ethnic identity in school were revealed. Three concepts were frequently emphasized about teachers’ behavior in the classroom. Four concepts were frequently emphasized about ethnic identity grouping in activities. Four concepts were frequently emphasized about ethnic identity in games and homeworks.

Keywords: Immigrant Students, Identity Development, Acculturation

1. Introduction

We live in an era in which the world changes fast and countries and nations are affected from this period. Increasing the demands, working areas and transportation opportunities of people with technological developments brought multinationalism and multiculturalism. As a result, almost all societies are unable to

maintain their culture, language, and identity structures (Berry, 2009). Berry states that this is related to the fact that people must leave their homeland for various reasons, in other words, they migrate. According to him, the reasons why people go to other countries can be categorized as; asylum, escape from war, work, education, and tourism as well as international trade and political relations which are the result of globalization in our age. All these factors, cited by an increase in the number of multinational countries bringing together communities of different ethnicities, are forcing more and more people to flee from their country as immigrants (Berry 2009). Methods that will make it easier for people to live together and in harmony in social life should be used in democratic and multinational countries that accept immigrants. A process called “acculturation” takes place while people learn to live together and adapt to each other (Berry, Phinney, Sam, and Vedder, 2006; Saygin & Hasta, 2018).

1.1. Acculturation

Acculturation was described by Flaskerud (2007) and Gibson (2001) as, the change caused by the interaction of one group with another. As a result of the interpersonal interaction between them in the acculturation process, changes occur in the language, values and behaviors of both the host society and the immigrant minority society. Despite these changes, it is stated that both groups continue to differ from each other in their essence (Flaskerud, 2007). The acculturation process affects both the host and immigrant society. However, some researchers (Berry, 2001; Bourhis & Dayan, 2004; Flaskerud, 2007; Rohmann, Piontkowski, & van Randenborgh, 2008) argue that immigrants are more affected by the acculturation process.

Eunyoung and Jeannette (2013) identified acculturation from psychological development aspect and stated that acculturation is an important concept used to explore immigrants’ psychological well-being, family conflict, and issues related with mental health. The ability of the culture process to work depends on the symbiotic contact between individuals or groups with different cultural backgrounds and the alien group’s adaptation to the new culture. For many immigrant-origin students, acculturation is an important issue. Scholars (Ferguson, Ferguson, & Ferguson, 2017; Schwartz, Unger, Zamboanga, & Szapocznik, 2010; Unger, Gallaher, Shakib, Ritt-Olson, Palmer & Johnson, 2002) point out that there are three dimensions of acculturation; (i) the behavioral dimension, which includes cultural practices such as language and media tours followed, (ii) the emotional dimension that corresponds to cultural identification, such as the individual’s sense of belonging to the country he/she had to abandon or migrate from, and (iii) the cognitive dimension, which defines the individual putting the needs of his/her family in front of his/her own.

Gordon’s One-Dimensional Cultivation Model (Gordon, 1964) and Berry’s Two-Dimensional Cultivation Model (Berry, 1980) are two basic approaches toward acculturation process. The One-Dimensional Cultivation Model was developed by Gordon in 1964. According to Gordon, there are two options for the immigrants. First, it adheres to its own culture, ethnic origin, values, behavior and attitude. The second option is to adapt to the culture of the country of migration. The Gordon model stipulates that successful cultural adaptation must break with all ethnic ties (Bourhis, Moise, Perreault, and Senecal, 1997). Therefore, Bourhis et al. (1997) evaluated this model as assimilation. This model has been criticized for being inadequate due to the two options it offers (eg Rogler, Cortes, and Malgady, 1991), after which a “two-dimensional cultivation model” has been developed, which takes acculturation more extensively. The Two-Dimensional Cultivation Model was developed by John W. Berry. Contrary to the one-dimensional culture model, according to this model, which deals with acculturation more extensively, minority or immigrant groups can maintain their essential cultural or self-cultural identity while maintaining socially necessary relations with the host society (Saygin & Hasta, 2018). When Berry first developed the model, he identified eight cultivation trends. However, today it is seen that the number of these approaches has decreased to four; integration, separation, assimilation, and marginality (Berry, 2001).

1.2. Identity development

The level of education in the migrated country, the language of the subject, gender, length of life in the host country, age, marital status, religion, social identity and social distance are variables that affect the culture and adaptation process. Identity development is a serious result of acculturation and adaptation process and related with social identity. Goodenow and Espin (1993) argued that considering some factors in the identity development process positively affects the identity development process of immigrant students. In this context, it would be correct to talk about three factors. The first factor is the problems individuals face after gaining immigrant status. Being a newcomer as well as belonging to the ethnic minority group can be given as examples of additional difficulties. The second factor is the old country's and the host country's perspective on gender equality. The third and the last factor argues that there is an interaction between the first two factors. Ethnic or cultural identity and gender are a whole in social life. They intersect with each other and are influenced by each other.

The individual's not losing his identity while adapting to the new culture and his ability to adopt his new identity in a healthy way makes the process of identity formation eccentric, especially when it comes to adapting to a new country and culture (Catalano, Fox, & Vandeyar, 2016). As a result, immigrant students are forced to choose between refusing to adapt to the new culture or adaptation very quickly. In addition, it is a necessity to adapt to the gender understanding of the culture they migrate into. Goodenow and Espin (1993) pointed out the difficulties that immigrant students may face in the process of identity development, and argued that the necessity to adapt to the new culture brings along a new understanding of gender and a balance skill that will make it easier to have a sense of belonging to both cultures.

Birman (1998) underlines that many factors affect the process of identity development, such as the social class or status in the old and new culture, the previously established closeness with the people of the immigrated country, the experiences that cause them to leave their country, the problems encountered in the new country and in the new social life there. Immigrants try to create a sense of meaning, identity and self-consciousness in everyday life in their new country. In doing so, they make use of the new culture's elements such as ethnic identity, racial characteristics, gender perception and social class structures. Rubin (2007) examined the identity development process of immigrant youth and concluded that the situation of those living in urban areas in particular is overlooked and among cultural practices and structural inequalities, their real life experiences with employees such as teachers, police forces and social workers should also be taken into account. For example, Syrian immigrant students will have a completely different experience of acculturation from the civil war in Syria. There are some advantages that immigrants can take advantage of in the process of adapting to the new culture; having friends or family with people from the host community, being able to enroll in a school that accepts immigrants and has an effective bilingual education program.

As Guerrero (1974) said, rapid acculturation has a possible effect on identity development. Being an immigrant, having to leave your homeland and living in a completely different country is not an easy thing. Combined with rapid cultural changes, Syrian immigrants feel like they are stuck in a cage. There are some cultural changes that await them in this cage such as erasing all traces of the Syrian culture and to reject all limitations imposed by the native culture, learning the values, norms and language of Turkish culture; wearing Turkish style clothes; changing their name to a Turkish name; listening to Turkish music and changing preferences and habits in social life by adapting to the Turkish culture. Although this situation may initially be perceived as a "progress" for Syrian immigrant community, a rapid or excessive change in cultural values may lead Syrian migrants to develop an untrue personality by detaching all of them from their core and rejecting everything about their old culture in their current psychological inventions.

1.3. Gender and identity development

Goodenow and Espin (1993) reported that gender, together with the influence of ethnic origins and immigration, is very influential in the identity development process of immigrants. Sexual maturity and sexual roles play a

key role in the transition from childhood to adulthood and in all areas of life. As with other areas of psychology, researchers in identity development preferred to focus specifically or primarily on men. The experiences of women in the process of identity development have recently begun to be studied. Although immigrants face the problems of culture as a whole, these problems do not affect men and women in the same way (Goodenow & Espin, 1993). Espin (1987), working on immigrants in the United States, demonstrated that the process of men adapting to the American culture is happening quickly, while women are expected to preserve their former cultures' roles and virtues. It is expected that there will be a conflict inappropriate sexual role behaviour and sexuality in this context. It is not difficult to predict that this conflict will be severe and permanent, especially in women who grow up in the old cultural environment (Espin, 1987). The degree of alienation of women and men in the new culture is quite different from each other and, according to Goodenow and Espin (1993), the contrast between the old culture and the new culture's gender roles can easily lead to a feeling of being in limbo.

1.4. Acculturation and identity development

It is compulsory for immigrant students to adapt to the culture of the country they migrate to, if they will not return back to their home country. Berry (1983) states that there may be different forms of cultural adaptation at this point. For example, immigrant students may become marginalized members of the new culture while continuing identity development process smoothly, or the cultural experience may result in failure. Studies (Cervantes, de Snyder ve Padilla, 1989; Jaycox, Stein, Kataoka, Wong, Fink, Escudero ve Zaragoza, 2002; Kartal, Alkemade, & Kiroopoulos, 2019; Torres-Matullo, 1980) have revealed that severe depression, post-traumatic stress disorder and other serious mental health problems are common among immigrants, and the problem of inability in adapting to school is common among immigrant students who have recently had to leave their country (First & Carrera, 1988; Frattini & Meschi, 2019; Olson, 1988).

Williams and Berry (1991) argued, from a multi-cultural point of view, that all migrants who migrate to a different country face opportunities and threats to their cultural and individual identities from the law under the pressure of psychological pressure or cultural adaptation. Changes in values, behaviors and credentials create the traditions of the culture to be adapted to. In this context, Kazempur and Hulli (2001) concluded that the socio-economic status, the length of life in the immigrated country, the support of parents and friends, and the socio-political structure of the new culture strongly influence the culture experience of immigrants.

1.5. Ethnic media and identity development

Ethnic identity, a form of cultural identity, is about how individuals and groups define and make sense of themselves in terms of the ethnic group to which they belong. Jeffres & Hur (1980) observed that ethnic media exist for ethnic groups that are not assimilated, isolated, and put their ethnic identities at the centre of their social lives. Wang (2006), on the other hand, argued that there is a positive relationship between ethnic media use, ethnic identity and ethnicity criteria. Ethnic media also reinforces ethnic identity and enables immigrants to retain their main cultural characteristics. Many immigrants who had to leave their country of origin and grow and migrate to a new country want to preserve their cultural ties and ethnic identity. Ethnic media are used to meet this need (Wang, 2006).

Research (Gülner, 2011; Lee & Tse, 1994; Viswanath & Arora, 2000) revealed that ethnic media has a striking effect on ethnic identity development and culture. While the dominant ethnic media negatively affects the culture in the long term, the ethnic media strengthens the ethnic identity and enables the immigrant society to protect its own culture. For example, Im (1998) reported that Korean migrants maintaining their roots loyalty led them to follow the Korean media more, not the American media. Findings also revealed that following the Korean media negatively affects their adaptation to the new culture (American culture). Data also show that empowerment of ethnic media plays a positive role in the process of ethnic identity development (Jeffres, 2000).

People who had to leave their country of birth and who were named immigrants face the ethnic identities they left behind while trying to adapt to the new culture. Ethnic identity presents a dynamic and multi-dimensional structure. Individuals who adopt their ethnic identity prefer to take part in group activities in their social lives in

their new countries, to have a sense of belonging, to get involved with the members of their own society, which is not appreciated by the new society, and to define themselves as a member of a particular ethnic group (Cokley, 2007). Identity development in the adopted country must be evaluated comprehensively, since the immigrant students left behind their first culture and meet a new one. And, within the scope of this research, both Syrian and Turkish cultures require a realistic appraisal and an adequate mourning for what has been lost. We aimed to understand the adaptation process, belonging to Turkish culture and ethnic identity development among Syrian students arriving in Turkey. How Syrian students develop a sense of belonging and adapt their identities to integrate with Turkish life and education is the main purpose of the study.

2. Method

2.1. Research design

The aim of the study is to evaluate the process of Syrian immigrant students' adaptation to Turkish culture and acquiring an ethnic identity, and to examine their comments on the new culture and the school where they were educated. Within the scope of the study, qualitative research method and phenomenological design were preferred among research approaches. The purpose of the phenomenological pattern is to reveal the perceptions and experiences of individuals about the facts that they are aware of but do not have detailed information about. The data source of this design is the individuals or groups who experience the phenomenon that the research focuses on and who can project or reflect it (Altunışık, 2002; Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2006).

2.2. Participants

Convenience sampling, which refers to the sample group that the researcher can easily reach, was preferred in determining the participants of the study. The reason for this preference is that it is economical and makes it possible to obtain more detailed information (Paton, 2001). Eight students who study at the school that receives the most immigration in Nizip district of Gaziantep province, who do not speak Turkish and who have identity conflict were selected as sampling group.

2.3. Data collection

The semi-structured interview form was used as data collection tool. Conducting the interview based on a pre-prepared interview protocol that provides more systematic and comparable information is the greatest convenience provided to a researcher by the semi-structured interview technique (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2006). Interviewing, on the other hand, according to Bogdan and Biklen (1998), is held with two or more people for a predetermined purpose and to obtain information. In the interview, the questions of the interviewer are answered by the participants and the researcher records these answers in various tools. Berg (1998) noted that interview questions are usually asked in a systematic and fixed order to the interviewer. Interviewer can ask the questions in any order they want during the interview and make explanations whenever he/she sees it when necessary (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2006). Belonging to school and class; the level of conversations about class, age, gender, nationality in their new schools; time spent in Turkey; socio-economic status of parents; ethnic identity and a new culture, education and harmony were the questions to be answered.

2.4. Data analysis

The data obtained from the questions asked to the students were analyzed by using thematic analysis technique. Yıldırım and Şimşek (2006) made some suggestions to researchers who want to make thematic analysis. In this research, the aforementioned suggestions were also used. The first step is to create a frame for analysis. This is followed by the second step, that is the processing of the data according to the thematic framework. The third step is to process the data according to the thematic frame. The definition and interpretation of the findings refers to the fourth and last step. The main purpose of the analysis is to present the data for readers, arranged and interpreted according to the determined themes. In this framework, the collected data are first described in a logical and understandable manner, the depicted data is interpreted, the cause-effect relationship between the

findings is examined and interpreted by the researcher and these comments are included in the discussion part. In this framework, the students' ideas, which were recorded with audio and video, were recorded in computer environment and concepts were created, without taking into account the misrepresentation and incorrect sentence structures and making any corrections. The names of the students participating in the interview were coded. The data obtained were re-integrated based on the concepts and made ready for interpretation (Adu, 2019; Silverman, 2001).

2.5. Reliability and validity

Internal validity (credibility) was tried to be ensured by expert examination, participant confirmation and keeping the duration of the interviews long. External validity was carried out by detailed description method. In order to examine whether the categories and concepts obtained were organized effectively or not, they were presented to the opinions of 2 experts and necessary arrangements were made in line with the suggestions.

3. Results

In this section answers of students are analyzed, and findings are as below:

Findings about experiences in the adaptation process:

First of all researchers aimed to learn what the students experienced while adapting to culture in Turkey. The following questions were asked to the students in order:

- Are there any events you experienced with your family to adapt to this culture? Did your family contribute to this adaptation process?
- Are there any events you experienced in the school to adapt to this culture? Did teachers and peers contribute to this process?
- Are there any events you experienced in the environment to adapt to this culture? Did your environment contribute to this process?
- How did these events that you experienced affect your ideas?

As a result of the content analysis, three categories and 12 concepts related to the adaptation process were revealed.

Figure 1: Views of the students about their families' contributions to adaptation process

As seen in the figure 1, 3 concepts were frequently emphasized about the actions of the family in the adaptation process. These are support for adaptation, lack of support for adaptation, support for learning language of new country. The statement of a student about the question is as follow:

“My father used to bring home a notebook with Turkish words and teach us Turkish from it.”

Figure 2: Views of the students about events that experienced in the school while adaptation process

As seen in the figure 2, 6 concepts were frequently emphasized about events that are experienced in the school while adaptation process. These are acceptance by peers, language proficiency causing acceptance, learning school norms, encouragement for language by students, encouragement for language by teachers, and fear about loneliness. The statement of a student about the question is as follow:

“All of my classmates helped me learn Turkish quickly.”

Figure 3. Views of the students about their environments’ contributions to adaptation process

As seen in the figure 3, three concepts were frequently emphasized about environments' contributions to adaptation process. These are encouragement for new language, encouragement for learning new things, help by neighbors and co-workers. The statement of a student about the question is as follow:

“I did not know Turkish and our neighbors and relatives encouraged me to read in Turkish and helped me learn Turkish.”

Figure 4: Views of the students about effects of events to ideas after migration

As seen in the figure 4, six concepts were frequently emphasized about effects of events to ideas after migration. These are feeling as a citizen, feeling as a part of school and class, feeling at home, feeling brotherhood and friendship, feeling in debt to the host country, and concern for moving to a new country. The statement of a student about the question is as follow:

“I did not know Turkish and our neighbors and relatives encouraged me to read in Turkish and helped me learn Turkish.”

3.1. Findings about belonging to new culture, school, class

Secondly researchers aimed to learn about students' belonging to the new culture, school, and class.

The following questions were asked to the students in order:

- Do you feel part of the new culture? Why?
- Do you feel like you belong to your school? Why?
- Do you feel like you belong to your class? Why?

As a result of the content analysis, three categories and 16 concepts related to belonging to new culture, school, and class were revealed.

Figure 5: Students' views on whether they feel part of new culture or not

As seen in the figure 5, six concepts were frequently emphasized whether they feel part of new culture or not. These are feeling as a citizen, feeling at home, feeling brotherhood and friendship, feeling in debt to the host country, and dislike own culture. The statement of a student about the question is as follow:

"This is a country I love and I want to pay my debt. I feel very indebted to this country."

Figure 6: Students' views on whether they feel belonging to the new school

As seen in the figure 6, four concepts were frequently emphasized whether they feel belonging to the new school. These are having native friends in school, child labor as a barrier to schooling, sense of belonging to school, acceptance by teachers and students. The statement of a student about the question is as follow:

"My teachers and friends support me. I won't stay here for even one second if they don't support."

Figure 7: Students' views on whether they feel belonging to the new class or not

As seen in the figure 7, 6 concepts were frequently emphasized whether they feel belonging to the new class. These are discrimination by peers, not alienation by peers, not alienation by teachers, sincerity with peers, social interaction with native peers, and assimilation for acceptance by Turkish peers. The statement of a student about the question is as follow:

“First, I was excluded, then they started to like me because I started learning Turkish. They did not like me before, but now they do. My friends never talked to me when I first arrived, but now they talk and consult me about everything.”

3.2. Findings about ethnic identity in school

Finally, the researchers aimed to learn students' experiences about their ethnic identity in school.

The following questions were asked to the students in order:

- *Do your teachers behave differently towards you based on your ethnic identity?*
- *How are groups determined in lessons that used grouping activities?*
- *Is your ethnic identity effective in doing homework and playing games with Turkish students?*

As a result of the content analysis, three categories and 11 concepts related to ethnic identity in school were revealed.

Figure 8: Views of the students about teachers' behavior in the lesson

As seen in the figure 8, three concepts were frequently emphasized about teachers' behavior in the lesson. These are not alienation by teachers, not biased teacher treatment, and positive treatment by teachers. The statement of a student about the question is as follow:

"I love my teachers because they do not discriminate students according to their ethnic identity."

Figure 9: Views of the students about ethnic identity grouping in activities

As seen in the figure 9, four concepts were frequently emphasized about *ethnic identity* grouping in activities. These are no discrimination while selection for groups, mixed ability grouping, mixed culture grouping in school/classroom, and multicultural groups. The statement of a student about the question is as follow:

"Our teacher says that you will not exclude your friends, when I ask a question, you will talk and answer together. As Syrians and Turks, we form a mixed group."

Figure 10: Views of the students about ethnic identity in games and homeworks

As seen in the figure 10, four concepts were frequently emphasized about *ethnic identity in games and homeworks*. These stay away from the game to avoid fight, game as a tool for inclusion into a group,

collaboration with native students for homework, and getting help from peers for homework. The statement of a student about the question is as follow:

“Before I came here, I didn't know the hopscotch game, but my neighborhood friends taught me it.”

4. Discussion

As a result of the content analysis, three categories and 12 concepts related to the adaptation process were highlighted. Three concepts were frequently emphasized about the attitudes of the family in the adaptation process. *These are supported* for adaptation, lack of support for adaptation, and support for learning language of the new country. Conflicts between old and new cultures can have serious effects on cultural adaptation and some actors can affect identity development negatively. Ellis & Chen (2013) explored the identity development progress of 11 undocumented college students living in the United States and concluded that older family members' traditional values that are part of their native culture affect immigrant children's identity development negatively. Six concepts were frequently emphasized about events that are experienced in the school during the adaptation process. *These are* acceptance by peers, language proficiency needed for acceptance, learning school norms, support for language learning by peer students, support for language learning by teachers, and fear about loneliness. Three concepts were frequently emphasized about environments' contributions to the adaptation process. *These are* encouragement to learn the new language, encouragement for learning new things, help by neighbors and co-workers. Rubin (2007), on the contrary, found that civic participation and positive attitudes toward civic participation affect identity development positively. Students who have experience of ideals and life's realities that reflect an alignment/harmony and who develop an active attitude in civic participation are affected by the identity development positively. Students who have experience of ideals and life's realities that reflect a nonalignment/disharmony and who develop an active attitude in civic participation are affected by the identity development positively. Students who have experience of ideals and life's realities that reflect a nonalignment/disharmony and who develop a passive attitude in civic participation are affected by the identity development negatively.

As a result of the content analysis, 3 categories and 16 concepts related to belonging to new culture, school, and class were highlighted. 6 concepts regarding how much the new culture was embraced by the immigrants, were frequently emphasized. These are feeling as a citizen, feeling at home, feeling brotherhood and friendship, feeling in debt to the host country, dislike of own culture. 4 concepts were frequently emphasized regarding how much belonging they feel for the new school. These are having native friends in school, child labor as a barrier to schooling, sense of belonging to school, acceptance by teachers and students. 6 concepts were frequently emphasized regarding how much belonging they feel for the new class. These are discrimination by peers, reconciliation by peers, reconciliation by teachers, frankness with peers, social interaction with native peers, and assimilation to be accepted by Turkish peers. Bresnahan and Kim (1993) researched international teaching assistants in the US and found out that the biggest dream of these assistants was getting an assistantship prize at a major US university but they were also a greatly concerned about facing US undergraduate hostility and racism. On the other hand, according to Çelik & İçduygu (2019) Syrian students systematically raised their concerns regarding bullying and unfavorable stereotypes they receive from their peers in and outside of school. Even though some of these students could come over these problems by seeking help from their teachers, many other felt left out, bullied, stigmatized and outcast while some can solve these problems by asking for help from their teachers, many felt depressed, stigmatized, bullied and alienated. Ham, Yang & Cha (2017) found that, students with a native language that is different from the education language at the school were more likely to develop a lesser feeling of belonging at school. Similarly, by investigating mental health worries and the dealing mechanisms of 274 Chinese, Japanese and Korean immigrant junior high and high school students, Yeh & Inose (2002) concluded that the all three Asian immigrant groups commonly faced problems of communication difficulties. Using the social support networks was reported as the most frequently used coping strategy and Japanese students were more prone to interpersonal problems.

As a result of the content analysis, 3 categories and 11 concepts related to ethnic identity in school were revealed. 3 concepts were frequently emphasized about teachers' behavior in the lesson. These are; reconciliation

by teachers, no biased teacher treatment and positive treatment by teachers. 4 concepts were frequently emphasized about ethnic identity grouping in activities. These are; no discrimination during the selection for groups, mixed ability grouping, mixed culture grouping in school/classroom, multicultural groups. 4 concepts were frequently emphasized about ethnic identity in games and homework. These are; to stay away from the game to avoid fight, game as a tool for inclusion into a group, collaboration with native students for homework, getting help from peers for homework. According to the school principals, overcrowded classrooms is one of the most significant problems in the physical condition of the schools as recorded by Sahin & Sumer (2018). Language and communication difficulties, ostracization, prejudice, differences in cultural backgrounds, factions within the students, fighting and integration difficulties are specified as the major problems between the Turkish and the Syrian students. The major behavioral problems of the Syrian student at school were determined to be absence from the school, lack of discipline, frequent change of residence, factions within the students, being held to a higher standard and discontent with the teacher. The language difficulties, communication issues, having teachers with different attitudes, sense of being an outcast, grouping and different cultural backgrounds come forward as the primary problems that teachers have Syrian students while communicating with them. Identity development is a sophisticated process which have multiple source of influence such as native and the host cultural factors. There is a constant exchange between these value systems. Identity is built as a product of these exchanges between the native and the host cultures influences. Identity development is a dynamic process. Cultural (native-host country), contextual (obstacles) and personal (endurance) elements impact the development of immigrant students' own identity. External elements (legal, financial and interpersonal obstacles) can affect identity development negatively (Ellis & Chen, 2013).

This research can be repeated with other samples and methods. The reasons as to why immigrant students do not have family support during the adaptation process, the reasons of negative attitudes of their peers towards immigrant students, the reasons for immigrant students' employment at a young age, the reasons for their fear of loneliness and the reasons for their reluctance to be involved in games with their peers can be investigated.

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